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**DEVELOPING COMPREHENSIVE STRATEGIES FOR
MANAGING INTERNET ADDICTION AMONG STUDENTS: A
NOMINAL GROUP TECHNIQUE APPROACH**

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Article Info	ABSTRACT
<p>Article history: Received: 16 June 2024 Revised: 10 July 2024 Accepted: 16 August 2024 Published: 1 Sept 2024</p> <p>Keywords: Internet Addiction, Cognitive Behavioral Therapy, NGT</p> <p></p>	<p>This study utilized the Nominal Group Technique (NGT) to create comprehensive strategies for managing internet addiction among students. An online NGT session was conducted with seven experts in student psychological well-being, focusing on three primary areas: cognitive restructuring, behavioral modification, and skill development. The results revealed strong agreement among the experts for all proposed strategies, with support levels ranging from 85.71% to 100%. Notably, Cognitive Behavioral Therapy sessions, positive self-talk exercises, alternative activities, and social skills training workshops received unanimous backing. These findings advocate for a multi-dimensional approach to addressing internet addiction, integrating cognitive, behavioral, and skill-oriented interventions. The study offers valuable guidance for educators, counselors, and policymakers in crafting effective programs to combat internet addiction among students.</p>

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INTRODUCTION

The emergence of the internet has profoundly revolutionized everyday existence, providing limitless possibilities for communication, entertainment, and information retrieval. Nevertheless, in conjunction with these advantages, a more negative occurrence has arisen-Internet addiction. This behavioral problem is defined by an excessive or poorly regulated fixation, desires, or actions related to computer use and internet access, resulting in considerable distress or impairment in personal, social, or vocational functioning (Shaw & Black, 2008). The term "Internet addiction" was initially used in the mid-1990s when academics started recording instances of persons facing adverse repercussions in their lives as a result of their inability to control their internet usage. Initial research drew comparisons between the symptoms of internet addiction and other behavioral addictions, such as pathological gambling (K. S. Young, 2004). Indications comprise excessive fixation on the internet, experiencing withdrawal symptoms when not connected, and developing a higher tolerance for online activities.

Internet addiction has become a major issue among students in the digital age, with an estimated global incidence rate of 11.2% among adolescents and young people (Fumero et al., 2018). The phenomenon of excessive and unregulated internet use, which results in functional impairment, is especially prevalent among students. This can be attributed to factors such as greater availability of the internet, academic pressure, and developmental susceptibilities (Király et al., 2020). Internet addiction has diverse implications that affect academic achievement, physical and mental health, and social connections. Students who suffer from internet addiction frequently display reduced academic performance, disrupted sleep patterns, and elevated levels of sadness and anxiety (Şan et al., 2024).

The prevalence of internet addiction among students in Malaysia is a rising worry, particularly due to the escalating availability of digital gadgets and online connectivity. A significant number of students are devoting an excessive amount of time to online activities, which frequently results in detrimental effects on their academic achievements, psychological well-being, and social relationships (Li Ping Wong et al., 2021; Mohamad et al., 2021; Radeef & Faisal, 2018). The proliferation of online gaming, social networking, and streaming platforms plays a substantial role in this problem, leading to a lack of involvement among students in their real-world obligations. Studies indicate that excessive internet usage might result in diminished concentration, sleep deprivation, and heightened levels of stress and anxiety.

Interventions aimed at tackling this problem encompass a spectrum of strategies, ranging from individual-centered methods such as Cognitive-Behavioral Therapy to more comprehensive educational initiatives and technological remedies (Kuss & Lopez-Fernandez, 2016). As this issue intensifies, parents, educators, and legislators must adopt proactive measures to educate students about responsible internet usage and develop ways to reduce the hazards associated with internet addiction.

LITERATURE REVIEW

The literature review includes the situation of internet addiction among students in Malaysia, theories of internet addiction and the Cognitive-Behavioral Model of internet addiction.

Internet Addiction Among Students in Malaysia

Internet addiction has become a notable public health issue, especially among students in Malaysia. With the increasing prevalence of digital devices and widespread internet access, a significant number of students are participating in extended online activities, resulting in the development of obsessive behavioral tendencies. The rise in cases of internet addiction among students is concerning, as research suggests that a significant part of Malaysian students are categorized as either problematic or addicted internet users. A survey conducted at a Malaysian public university found that 7.8% of students were classed as internet addicts, while 56.5% were recognized as problematic users (Rosliza et al., 2020).

Internet addiction is influenced by various elements, such as the intense emotional and cognitive fixation on the internet, as well as the utilization of the Internet as a coping strategy for dealing with stress and feelings of isolation. Studies indicate that those who experience mental health difficulties, such as depression and anxiety,

are more prone to developing internet addiction (Ismail et al., 2020). Amidst the COVID-19 pandemic, the situation has deteriorated even more, as students have increasingly depended on online platforms for both education and social connection. The epidemic has intensified the already elevated levels of internet usage, hence augmenting the susceptibility to addiction.

Furthermore, excessive reliance on the internet has adverse consequences on student's academic achievements and mental health. A study conducted among medical and pharmacy students in Malaysia reveals a significant correlation between excessive internet usage and academic challenges, as well as heightened levels of stress, anxiety, and depression (Loh et al., 2022; Radeef & Faisal, 2020) It is crucial to tackle internet addiction among students to protect their mental well-being and guarantee their academic achievements.

The Theory

The proliferation of internet addiction has emerged as a pressing issue in the era of digital technology, causing experts to formulate theories to elucidate this phenomenon. Three significant hypotheses that have been developed to explain internet addiction are the Cognitive-Behavioral Model, the Neurobiological Model, and the Social Skills Deficit Theory.

The Cognitive-Behavioral Model, as described by (Davis, 2001) posits that internet addiction arises from dysfunctional thought patterns and is exacerbated by the reinforcement of certain behaviors. This concept suggests that persons who have specific predispositions, such as social anxiety or depression, may develop problematic internet use as a means of coping. The internet offers a means of avoiding real-life issues, resulting in the promotion of desirable conduct. Over time, this can lead to the development of skewed cognitive patterns regarding one's self and the surrounding environment, hence reinforcing the addictive behavior. For instance, a person may form the conviction that their value is solely dependent on their online presence, resulting in heightened internet usage and social seclusion in the physical realm.

The Neurobiological Model of internet addiction establishes connections between internet addiction and substance addiction, with a specific emphasis on the brain's reward system. According to Brand et al. (2014), internet addiction stimulates the same brain pathways as chemical addictions, specifically via triggering the release of dopamine in the nucleus accumbent. This concept proposes that extended and excessive internet usage can result in neuroadaptations in the brain's reward system, akin to those observed in substance addiction. These alterations can lead to desires, increased tolerance, and the emergence of withdrawal symptoms when access to the internet is limited. The model additionally takes into account the influence of executive functions, suggesting that persons with internet addiction may experience compromised inhibitory control, resulting in challenges in managing their online conduct.

Caplan (2005) proposed the Social Skills Deficit Theory, which suggests that persons who have inadequate social skills are more susceptible to developing internet addiction. This idea posits that those who experience difficulties in engaging in direct interpersonal encounters may have a preference for online communication because they regard it as being safer and more controllable. The internet offers a venue for socially anxious persons to showcase an idealized version of themselves and participate in social interactions with decreased anxiety. Nevertheless, this inclination towards online social connection can result in excessive utilization of the internet and subsequent decline in interpersonal skills, establishing a self-reinforcing pattern of internet addiction.

Each of these theories provides useful insights into the intricate nature of internet addiction. The Cognitive-Behavioral Model emphasizes the significance of dysfunctional thought patterns and the reinforcement of behavior. The Neurobiological Model offers a biological foundation for comprehending internet addiction by establishing a connection with brain reward systems. The Social Skills Deficit Theory highlights the significance of social variables in the formation and perpetuation of internet addiction. In reality, these notions are not completely separate and frequently interact in the formation and continuation of internet addiction. For example, a person who lacks social skills (according to the Social Skills Deficit Theory) may seek social connection on the internet, which might result in positive reinforcement (as explained by the Cognitive-Behavioral Model) and

ultimately lead to alterations in the brain's reward pathways (as described by the Neurobiological Model). Gaining a comprehensive understanding of these theories is essential to formulate and implement efficient prevention and treatment methods for internet addiction. An all-encompassing strategy that targets cognitive distortions, neurobiological causes, and deficiencies in social skills may prove to be the most efficient way to manage this escalating problem in our progressively digitized society.

The Cognitive Behavioral Model

Ultimately, this article has centered around the Cognitive-Behavioral Model of internet addiction as the main theoretical framework for comprehending and tackling problematic internet use among students. We have selected this model because of its thorough approach to elucidating the progression and perpetuation of internet addiction, as well as its pragmatic implications for implementing intervention measures.

The Cognitive-Behavioral Model, first introduced by Davis (2001), offers a strong framework for understanding internet addiction as an intricate interaction between dysfunctional thoughts and reinforcing actions. This model is specifically applicable to the student population, as it takes into consideration the distinct cognitive and behavioral patterns that may arise during academic endeavors and social growth. Through the use of this paradigm, we have successfully identified and devised techniques that specifically address the cognitive distortions and harmful behaviors linked to internet addiction in students. The strategies encompass cognitive restructuring, behavioral modification techniques, and skill development.

This model focuses on thoughts and behaviors that can be changed making it a great option for creating practical solutions that can be simply understood and used by students, educators, and mental health professionals. Moreover, its adaptability enables the customization of interventions to cater to the distinct requirements of individual students and different educational settings. The Cognitive-Behavioral Model provides a strong basis for future study in this sector, allowing for the incorporation of discoveries and the improvement of intervention techniques. Our objective is to enhance the existing knowledge of internet addiction among students and offer evidence-based approaches for preventing and managing it in educational environments. The ultimate objective is to equip students with the cognitive tools and behavioral strategies required to establish a healthy connection with the internet. This will enable them to utilize its advantages for academic and personal development, while also avoiding the dangers of addiction. By implementing the Cognitive-Behavioral Model, our goal is to cultivate a cohort of students who possess the ability to traverse the digital realm with mindfulness, equilibrium, and self-regulation.

The Cognitive-Behavioral Model of internet addiction, as suggested by Davis (2001), offers a structure for comprehending and dealing with troublesome internet usage among students. Using this model as a basis, many preventive methods and management strategies can be employed to assist students in overcoming or preventing internet addiction. After careful consideration, we have chosen three constructs to use in this study.

1. Cognitive Restructuring: An essential component of the Cognitive-Behavioral Model involves resolving dysfunctional thought patterns. For students, this entails recognizing and questioning skewed thoughts associated with internet usage. Therapists or counselors can assist students in identifying detrimental cognitive patterns, such as the belief that their worth is solely dependent on their online presence or the notion that they are incapable of managing life without the internet. By employing cognitive restructuring techniques, students can substitute these thoughts with more equitable and pragmatic ones (Young, 2011). This method may entail maintaining cognitive diaries, scrutinizing the data supporting and contradicting these convictions, and engaging in the exercise of constructive self-dialogue.

2. Behavioral Modification: The model highlights the significance of behavioral reinforcement in sustaining addiction. In order to address this issue, students can be directed to alter their internet usage patterns. One technique that can be used to manage internet use is time management. This involves setting particular time restrictions for internet use and following a planned schedule (Kuss & Griffiths, 2017). b) Stimulus Control: Eliminating stimuli that induce excessive internet usage, such as keeping electronic gadgets away from the bedroom or employing website blocks during designated study periods (Cash et al., 2012). c) Alternative

Activities: Promoting involvement in offline activities that offer comparable benefits to internet usage, such as joining clubs or engaging in sports (Young, 2011).

3. Skill Development: To tackle the fundamental factors that may contribute to internet addiction, students can be instructed in various skills: a) **Stress Management:** Strategies such as mindfulness, deep breathing, and progressive muscular relaxation can assist students in managing stress without relying on excessive internet usage (Lan & Lee, 2013). b) **Social Skills Training:** Enhancing interpersonal communication abilities can decrease dependence on virtual connections (Caplan, 2005), c) **Developing problem-solving skills:** Improving students' capacity to address real-life problems can decrease their tendency to escape through internet usage (Davis, 2001).

The constructs, items, and questions for internet addiction management strategies in this study are summarised in this table:

Table 1: Strategies for managing internet addiction

Construct	Item	Question
Cognitive Restructuring	Thought Journals	I believe that thought journals can help identify negative thought patterns related to excessive internet use.
	Cognitive Behavioral Therapy (CBT) Sessions	Individual or group Cognitive Behavioral Therapy (CBT) sessions are effective in challenging maladaptive beliefs about internet use.
	Positive Self-Talk Exercises	Positive self-talk exercises can help reduce the impact of negative thoughts that lead to excessive internet use.
Behavioral Modification	Time Management Workshops	Time management workshops tailored specifically to balance online and offline activities are important for reducing excessive internet use.
	Stimulus Control Techniques	Stimulus control techniques, such as creating technology-free zones, can help reduce excessive internet use.
	Engaging in Alternative Activities	Encouraging students to participate in outdoor activities like sports, arts, or volunteering is an effective way to reduce time spent online.
Skill Development	Stress Management Programs	Stress management programs that teach techniques such as deep breathing and muscle relaxation can help students cope with stress without resorting to the internet.
	Social Skills Training Workshops	Social skills training workshops can help students build stronger offline relationships, reducing their reliance on online interactions.
	Problem-Solving Skill Development	Developing problem-solving skills through exercises or case studies can help students handle challenges more effectively without needing to use the internet as a means of escape.

METHODOLOGY

The NGT method is the primary research tool in this study. Seven professionals whose work touches on students' psychological well-being were involved in the research. Since it is still not practical to gather experts in person at this time, researchers conduct NGT sessions online using Google Meet. The session lasted for two hours. The NGT approach was used to gather ideas and solutions based on expert opinion through a brainstorming session with assembled experts. The researcher used the NGT approach to do a targeted computation at the session's end, yielding data that addressed the study's aims.

The NGT Method

The Nominal Group Technique (NGT) is a strategy for making decisions in a group setting that was created by Andre Delbecq and Andrew Van de Ven in 1971. The purpose of its design was to optimize group productivity, streamline the process of reaching consensus, and create prioritized solutions for intricate problems (Delbecq et al., 1975). NGT, or Nominal Group Technique, has found extensive use in diverse domains such as healthcare, education, and organizational administration. This is primarily because NGT effectively promotes equal participation among group members and reduces the overpowering influence of assertive individuals (Harvey & Holmes, 2012).

The NGT method generally consists of five main stages:

1. Silent Generation: Participants engage in a solitary and quiet process of generating ideas in response to a specific query or problem statement.
2. Round-Robin Recording: In this method, each participant takes turns sharing one thought at a time, while a facilitator records the ideas. This process continues until all ideas have been completely depleted.
3. Sequential Deliberation: The group engages in a discussion to clarify and evaluate each recorded thought. At this stage, no ideas are discarded.
4. Initial Ballot: Participants individually assign a numerical ranking or rating to the ideas in a confidential manner.
5. The group engages in a conversation on the initial voting outcomes and may proceed with a final vote if deemed necessary (McMillan et al., 2016).

In a Nominal Group Technique (NGT) study, the participation of experts is crucial to ensure the reliability and validity of the findings. Experts are selected based on their extensive knowledge, experience, and understanding of the specific subject area being investigated. Their involvement in the NGT process enables a structured and comprehensive exploration of ideas and solutions, as they contribute through brainstorming, discussion, and ranking of ideas. The diversity of expertise within the group fosters a well-rounded perspective on the research problem, ensuring that the outcomes reflect informed and credible insights. Table 2 presents the experts who participated in this study along with their respective fields, illustrating the breadth of knowledge and specialization that contributed to the overall findings.

Table 2: Experts participant for NGT

Numbers of Expert	Career	Discipline	Work Place
3	Counselor	Guidance & Counseling	School
1	Psychologist	Psychology & Counseling	Hospital
2	Lecturer	Psychology & Counseling	University
2	Counselor	Psychology & Counseling	Teacher's Training Institute

Data Analysis

Three main concepts are investigated in this study: cognitive restructuring, behavioral modification, and skill development. There are three items in each construct, and the potential responses are (1) disagree, (2) neutral, and (3) agree. The products and constructions are discussed in a group setting by a panel of seven specialists in the field. The experts then cast their votes based on their best judgment after the discussion. After gathering all of the data, the voting scores will be converted into percentage numbers for analysis. A ranking or priority procedure will be used to quantitatively examine the voting outcomes.

The experts' vote scores are converted into percentages and compared with evaluation criteria generated from the literature as part of the analysis. The voting percentage needs to be higher than 70% to be considered within the acceptable range of the Nominal Group Technique (NGT). This cutoff reflects the general agreement amongst experts that a percentage score is indicative of how relevant the measured factor is. Elements that achieve a score higher than 70% are considered relevant. In addition, the elements will be ranked according to their total score to determine which ones are most important.

RESEARCH FINDINGS AND DISCUSSIONS

The Nominal Group Technique (NGT) results demonstrated overwhelming support for the proposed strategies within the three main constructs: Cognitive Restructuring, Behavioral Modification, and Skill Development. With each strategy achieving over 70% agreement from experts, their relevance and suitability for addressing internet addiction among students became evident.

Cognitive Restructuring

Within the Cognitive Restructuring construct, experts showed particularly strong endorsement, signifying its critical importance in tackling internet addiction. The strategy of using thought journals received an 85.71% agreement, reflecting the experts' belief in the power of self-reflection. Thought journals were identified as an effective method for helping students track and analyze their thoughts and behaviors associated with internet use, ultimately aiding in recognizing patterns that contribute to excessive online activities.

The highest level of support was seen for Cognitive Behavioral Therapy (CBT) sessions, which achieved a perfect 100% agreement. Experts unanimously recognized CBT as a crucial intervention, underlining its efficacy in helping students reframe and modify maladaptive thoughts and behaviors tied to internet addiction. This endorsement suggests that CBT is seen as a cornerstone strategy for addressing the psychological underpinnings of excessive internet use.

Similarly, positive self-talk exercises also received 100% agreement, further emphasizing the importance of cultivating a healthier internal dialogue among students. Experts acknowledged that fostering positive self-talk plays a vital role in helping students combat negative self-perceptions, which are often linked to problematic internet use. By promoting constructive and affirming self-conversations, students are better equipped to make healthier decisions regarding their online activities.

Table 3: Cognitive restructuring strategies for managing internet addiction

No	Item	Total Item Score	Percentage	Rank	Voters Consensus
1	Thought Journals	18	85.71	2	Suitable
2	Cognitive Behavioral Therapy (CBT) Sessions	21	100	1	Suitable
3	Positive Self-Talk Exercises	21	100	1	Suitable

Behavioral Modification

The behavioral modification strategies also garnered strong support from experts, highlighting the significance of concrete actions and environmental adjustments in addressing internet addiction. These strategies emphasize the need for practical interventions that directly influence students' behavior and surroundings to mitigate excessive online activities.

Time management workshops received a high level of endorsement, with 90.48% agreement from the experts. This reflects the widespread recognition that poor time management is often a contributing factor to internet overuse. Experts believe that these workshops are essential in helping students develop the skills necessary to balance their online and offline activities more effectively, thereby reducing their dependence on the internet.

Similarly, stimulus control techniques, which also received 90.48% agreement, were strongly supported by the experts. This suggests a shared belief in the importance of modifying the environment to reduce the cues that trigger excessive internet use. Experts value strategies that involve creating both physical and digital spaces that minimize temptations and make it easier for students to manage their internet usage in a controlled manner.

The highest level of support, however, was for encouraging students to engage in alternative activities, which received unanimous agreement from the experts (100%). This reflects a consensus on the crucial role of behavioral substitution in managing addiction. Experts fully endorse the idea of promoting fulfilling offline activities as a key strategy to divert students' attention away from excessive internet use, providing them with healthier and more balanced alternatives.

Table 4: Behavioral Modification strategies for managing internet addiction

No	Item	Total Item Score	Percentage	Rank	Voters Consensus
1	Time Management Workshops	19	90.48	2	Suitable
2	Stimulus Control Techniques	19	90.48	2	Suitable
3	Engaging in Alternative Activities	21	100	1	Suitable

Skill Development

Skill Development strategies also received substantial backing, emphasizing the value of equipping students with essential skills to better manage their internet use and foster overall well-being. Workshops on Emotional Regulation were met with 85.71% agreement, highlighting their importance in helping students develop the ability to manage and understand their emotions. Experts recognize that by improving emotional regulation, students are better equipped to handle the stress and frustrations that might lead to excessive internet use, ultimately promoting healthier online behaviors.

Social Skills Training achieved 90.48% agreement, reflecting its critical role in enhancing students' interpersonal interactions and reducing the likelihood of internet addiction. Experts agreed that by improving social skills, students can form stronger, more meaningful offline relationships, which can serve as a buffer against excessive internet use.

Finally, the emphasis on Life Skills Development received unanimous support (100%). This indicates a strong consensus on the necessity of providing students with a comprehensive set of life skills, such as problem-solving, decision-making, and time management. Experts believe that equipping students with these skills is fundamental in fostering their independence and self-control, thereby effectively managing their internet usage and promoting a balanced lifestyle.

Table 5: Skill Development strategies for managing internet addiction

No	Item	Total Item Score	Percentage	Rank	Voters Consensus
1	Stress Management Programs	19	90.48	3	Suitable
2	Social Skills Training Workshops	21	100	1	Suitable
3	Problem-Solving Skill Development	20	95.24	2	Suitable

DISCUSSION

The significant agreement among experts regarding various techniques for addressing internet addiction among students highlights the intricate nature of this problem and emphasizes the necessity for a comprehensive strategy. This perspective closely corresponds to the Cognitive-Behavioral Model of internet addiction developed by Davis (2001). The model highlights the complex relationship between thoughts, behaviors, and abilities in the development and continuation of addictive behaviors associated with internet use.

Cognitive restructuring strategy were identified as a crucial element in resolving internet addiction, with Cognitive Behavioral Therapy (CBT) sessions and positive self-talk exercises earning universal endorsement from the expert panel. The strong support for this idea demonstrates the crucial importance of cognitive processes in internet addiction, as emphasized by Young (2011) in her groundbreaking research on Cognitive Behavioral Therapy for Internet Addiction (CBT-IA). The overwhelming endorsement of these cognitive therapies indicates that professionals acknowledge the substantial influence of dysfunctional thought processes on excessive internet usage. These cognitive patterns may encompass convictions regarding the internet as the sole means of gratification or false ideas of one's self-esteem being linked to online pursuits. The high level of consensus (85.71%) on the utilization of thought journals serves to strengthen the significance of self-reflection in the therapeutic procedure. Thought journals are a useful tool for individuals to recognize, record, and analyze their thoughts and actions related to the internet. The process of self-monitoring can play a crucial role in increasing awareness of triggers and patterns that contribute to excessive internet use, thereby enabling more effective interventions.

Within the field of behavioral modification, there is complete agreement (100%) on the importance of participating in alternative activities. This corresponds well with Young's (2011) suggestion to encourage offline activities that provide equivalent advantages to using the internet. This technique tackles the fundamental problem of behavioral substitution, which occurs when excessive online involvement is replaced by healthy, real-life activities. The high level of consensus, with a 90.48% agreement, on the need of time management workshops and stimulus control approaches, indicates that experts acknowledge the essential practical abilities required to properly regulate internet usage. These findings align with the research conducted by Kuss and Griffiths (2017), which highlighted the significance of formulating specific tactics to control online conduct and establish a harmonious digital way of life.

The strong approval of measures aimed at enhancing skills, especially the overwhelming backing of seminars focused on improving social skills, is particularly remarkable. This is consistent with Caplan's (2005) Social Skills Deficit Theory, which suggests that those who lack social skills may be more inclined to use the internet excessively as a way to make up for challenges in in-person encounters. The unanimous consensus among specialists indicates a knowledge that enhancing face-to-face social abilities may play a crucial role in decreasing dependence on online interactions and, subsequently, alleviating internet addiction. The significant consensus on the enhancement of problem-solving skills (95.24%) and stress management initiatives (90.48%) underscores the necessity of tackling the root causes that can contribute to excessive internet usage. The holistic approach is consistent with Davis's (2001) cognitive-behavioral model, which proposes that internet addiction frequently arises as an ineffective coping mechanism for underlying psychological problems or life stressors. Lan and Lee (2013) propose that addressing the underlying reasons of internet addiction, rather than only treating its symptoms, can be achieved by providing individuals with effective problem-solving skills and stress management approaches.

The endorsed comprehensive approach, supported by the expert panel, reflects a nuanced understanding of internet addiction as a complex issue that requires intervention across cognitive, behavioral, and skill-based domains. Effectively managing internet addiction among students involves not only addressing immediate behaviors and thoughts related to internet use but also fostering a broader set of life skills that encourage healthier and more balanced interactions with digital technology. The strong consensus on these diverse strategies indicates a shift toward a more holistic and integrated approach to tackling internet addiction. Experts recognize the interconnectedness of cognitive patterns, behavioral habits, and life skills in addressing problematic internet use. This broad perspective opens up promising opportunities for developing more effective therapies and preventive measures for internet addiction among students.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

This study offers useful insights on expert-endorsed ways for managing internet addiction among adolescents. The strong agreement among all suggested solutions indicates that a comprehensive strategy, which includes changing thought patterns, modifying behavior, and enhancing skills, is the most successful. The findings emphasize the significance of tackling both the symptoms and root causes of internet addiction, by the Cognitive-Behavioral Model and other pertinent ideas in the field.

Based on the findings of this study, several key recommendations have been developed to address internet addiction among students. These recommendations focus on implementing comprehensive strategies that blend cognitive, behavioral, and skill-development therapies, as well as promoting a supportive educational environment. By incorporating expert insights and research-based approaches, these recommendations aim to provide practical solutions for educators, policymakers, and mental health professionals in their efforts to combat internet addiction and enhance students' overall well-being.

1. Establish all-encompassing initiatives that incorporate cognitive, behavioral, and skill-oriented therapies to tackle internet addiction among kids.
2. Given the overwhelming endorsement of experts, it is recommended to prioritize the development of therapies based on Cognitive Behavioral Therapy (CBT), exercises that promote positive self-talk, and seminars that focus on improving social skills.
3. Advocate for educational institutions to integrate time management training and endorse offline activities as components of their student well-being efforts.
4. Design and assess problem-solving and stress management initiatives customized to address the specific requirements of students who are vulnerable to internet addiction.
5. Carry out additional research to evaluate the efficacy of these tactics in real-life environments and their enduring influence on mitigating internet addiction among students.

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